

POST COVID-19 CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES FOR A SUSTAINABLE FASHION RETAIL- CASE FROM ROMANIA

Author(s)*: Sunhilde CUC¹, Simina Teodora HORA², Cristina SECAN³

Position: Assoc. Prof., Ph.D.¹, PhD student², Lecturer, PHD³

University: University of Oradea

Address: Oradea, Universitatii Str., No. 1, Romania

Email: sunhilde_cuc@yahoo.com¹, horasimina@gmail.com² cris_secan@yahoo.com³

Webpage: <http://www.uoradea.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – This study is carried out to analyze the impact of COVID-19 on the fashion industry, and the opportunities for growth in the actual turbulent environment.

Methodology/approach - The methodology followed for this study involves a review of related literature and a quantitative online survey. Both primary and secondary data were collected for this study. Primary data was collected through 276 questionnaires, and the secondary data was gathered through internet search from research results from national and international statistical reports.

Findings – Second-hand clothes shopping becomes an alternative for responsible consumption, towards a circular economy, as an opportunity for fashion retail diversification. The reuse of textiles is a niche activity and is less costly than upstream initiatives to change the design, and production from a circular economy perspective.

Research limitations/implications – The limitations of the study are that the sample was restricted to the region of Central and Nord-West Romania.

Practical implications – Results of this study could be used by different actors – such as retailers, fashion designers, and education institutions, focusing on engaging consumers in active roles that foster Circular Economy success.

Originality/value – The study fills a gap in the literature on the subject of sustainable fashion in Romania.

Key words: Circular economy, fashion industry, second-hand clothes shopping (SHCS)

Introduction

The fashion industry was one of the hardest affected by the COVID-19 pandemic which led to the temporary closure of traditional physical stores around the world and made people stay home longer and stop spending money on clothes, shoes, and fashion accessories. (Zhao, 2022)

Unfortunately, the new SARS-CoV-2 variants (EDCE,2022), the monkeypox (Kozlov,2022), and the invasion of Ukraine do not predict the recovery of the industry as we use to know it soon. With decreased disposable income (e.g. inflation) and other external factors (e.g., lockdowns), consumers will be more aware and will chose to spend less on apparel, reduce discounts and impulse purchases. Consumers substantially use to reduce their spending on fashion during uncertain economical condition, quickly identifying clothes, shoes, and fashion accessories as a 'non-essential' category of consumer goods. (Aurora et al, 2020). In addition to the economical state, due to environmental concerns, more and more customers are considering the larger impact of their consumption on other people, animals, or the environment (Pereira et al, 2021). This type of consumer either decides to buy less clothing and bases his fashion consumption on strict necessity; either they move towards circular economy models and decide to extend the life cycle of clothing products among the methods used being the purchase of second-hand clothing.

The structure of this paper is divided into three parts: (1) Literature review; (2) Methodology; (3) Findings and conclusions. The literature review enables a general view of the fashion industry, second-hand clothing, and consumer behavior related to second-hand shopping. For the methodology, a quantitative

analysis is done in the form of an online survey using a questionnaire applied to a sample of 276 young fashion customers. All data will be discussed in the chapter on findings and conclusions.

Literature review

The Covid-19 pandemic has changed consumer behavior. With the uncertainty of the situation, consumers have concentrated on their basic needs and purchasing mainly essential products (Lopez and Quattara, 2021). Therefore, the fashion industry recorded a 20% decline in revenues during 2019–2020. As the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic continued to run its course, the performance inequalities that have become a challenge over recent years were more in evidence than ever. According to the latest report of the McKinsey Global Fashion Index (McKinsey, 2022), a record of 69% of companies reported a drastic decline in 2020, compared with 61% in 2019 and only 28% in 2011. About 7% of companies left the market either due to financial distress or because they were acquired by competitors.

According to McKinsey (2022) the main opportunities for the growth of the fashion industry are digitalization and consumer engagement while supply chain pressures will challenge the industry in 2022. Sustainability is considered both an opportunity for growth and also challenge. More than ever, sustainability is dominating consumer priorities and the fashion agenda. There is a rising customer interest in second-hand retail stores and platforms to buy fashion products (Evans et al, 2022). Second-hand shopping, involves buying products previously owned or used, and then sold, typically for lower prices than new and is one of the most sustainable ways to shop. It is a popular trend in fashion, especially among young people, because of ethical and environmental concerns and among older generation because of economical reasons (Wiederhold and Martinez, 2018). It is becoming a global phenomenon, expected to grow 127% by 2026.(ThredUp, 2022)

According to ThredUp (2022) the global second-hand apparel market will grow 3 times faster than the global apparel market overall. The number of second-hand stores is growing as stigma of being associated with the lower-income class and barriers to second-hand shopping decrease (Zaman et al., 2019), as the consumer and the second-hand online market is expected to grow from 7 billion USD in 2019 to 36 billion USD in 2024. (Smith, 2022).

From eliminating manufacturing pollution to closing the loop and eliminating the need for unsustainable materials, secondhand fashion promotes a circular economy. In recent years big fashion retailers like H&M, ASOS, and Urban Outfitters enter the secondhand space.

Sustainability in retail has become an important subject leading retail trends through its relevance across a wide range of fields (e.g. environmental sciences, business, and social sciences) and terms (e.g. sustainable development, sustainable supply chain, supply chain management, and corporate social responsibility). (Ruiz-Real et al, 2018)

The main types of retailers of secondhand fashion are traditional brick-and-mortar stores with physical locations, for profit (retail or consignment stores) or non-profit retail outlets stores (thrift shops), open markets, and online platforms.

Figure 1. Trading platforms for second-hand clothing (SHC) Source: by authors

The advantage of brick-and-mortar stores (including thrift stores and consignment stores) is that customers can visit, buy, and interact with the products. Fashion products sold in thrift stores usually have superior quality to the fast fashion currently produced (Edbring et al., 2016).

Open markets, including street markets, or flea markets are organized gatherings of individual stalls selling unique and unpredictable secondhand objects. The advantage is that the customers can interact with the products, negotiate and then buy.

Online stores are e-commerce platforms selling a vast range of items, and offering users the possibility to search and buy (B2C) or to buy or sell and interact with others through the platform (C2C). The spreading of C2C contributed to the development of second-hand products markets, like online auction-based sites e.g. eBay, and Amazon (Liao & Chu, 2013) or the websites that allow private people to trade (buy and sell) goods online e.g. OLX, eBay, Sellpy, Remixshop, etc.

In Romania, the most present are the privately-owned, for-profit businesses stores that resell clothes imported from the main western markets (Great Britain, Germany, Holland). (Cuc, 2016)

Methodology

Analysis of statistical reports and a quantitative research method were applied for this study. We provide an overview of the immediate impact of COVID-19 on the fashion industry based on a qualitative analysis of recent statistical data. To investigate why some consumers, embrace, and others avoid, second-hand shopping (Edbring et al., 2016, Ferraro et al., 2016) and also to study consumer shopping behavior across physical secondhand store formats, and online platforms a quantitative online survey of young people was administered.

An online questionnaire study was conducted in June 2022. This study chose young educated adults aged between 18 and 40, living in Central and West Romania as the primary data source. An online self-administered questionnaire was selected as the data collection method. The survey, created on Google Forms, was distributed on diverse social media platforms (Facebook, WhatsApp) whereby respondents were asked to redirect the questionnaire to people corresponding the desired sample characteristics. The questionnaire was designed based on the previous literature and was pre-tested and redesigned through a sample of 10 bachelor's and master's students by undertaking the pilot study work (Ropa and Rani, 2012).

To explore how consumer orientations differ in terms of secondhand shopping frequency and secondhand retail platforms, participants were asked to indicate their interest in secondhand clothing and if had ever purchased secondhand, the frequency with which they buy, and the type of stores they buy from. To reduce socially desirable responses, participants were informed that the anonymity of their responses was guaranteed, and their answers will be treated as confidential and will be only used for academic purposes.

Discussion and conclusions

Romania produces clothes, textile fibers, and footwear worth 18.3 billion lei (3.7 billion Euro) annually. In 2021, the industry lost 3.7 million lei in turnover. In 2021 the clothing sector marked a 53,79% decrease compared to 2020 and the footwear sector decrease with 45,46% (RISCO,2022). In terms of the number of companies, almost 750 have vanished from the statistics. The fashion sales sector suffered less, around 6.3% (2020), and for 2022 the retail sector is expected to return with a slight increase of around 3% to a value of around 2.35 billion EUR. Footwear retail saw the biggest drop (-24%), followed by the biggest increase (+10%) post-pandemic.(MKOR,2022). The economic crisis aggravated by the two years of SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, the energy crisis, inflation, and the war in Ukraine may have a significant impact on clothing consumption practices, due to the decrease in the purchasing power of a large part of the Romanian population, resulting in increased demand for products with more affordable prices.

Table 1 shows the basic characteristics of the consumer surveyed. Out of the 276 respondents surveyed, 187 (67.75%) were female and 89 (32.25%) were male. Out of the total surveyed consumers, a substantial proportion, 48 % of the respondents were between 30 to 40 years of age. The educational profile of the respondents' shows that most of them are bachelor's or master's students (75%). The high

percentage of respondents with income below the minimum wage in the economy (about 25%) is given by their student's status; not reflected necessarily a precarious social situation.

Table 1. Sample characteristics

Sample characteristics		Frequency	Percentage	Never by SHC		
				Frecvency	Percentage	Percentage
Gender	Male	89	32.25	17	19,1	11,23
	Female	187	67.75	14	7,5	
Age group	18-25	105	38.04	10	9.52	
	26-30	39	14.13	3	7.69	
	31-40	130	47.10	18	13.85	
	40+	2	0.72	0	0	
Education	High school students	128	46.4	15	11.72	
	University-Bachelor	83	30.1	7	8.43	
	University-Master	56	20.3	6	10.71	
	University-Doctoral studies	9	3.3	3	33.33	
Net monthly income	Less 1500 lei * (cca 300 Euro)	71	25.72	4	5.63	
	1501-3500 lei (300-700 Euro)	121	43.84	10	8.26	
	Above 3500 lei (700 Euro)**	84	30.44	17	20.24	

*minim wage on economy

**medium wage on economy

The results revealed that 28.26% of the surveyed sample buys SHC clothing regularly, 28.62% occasionally, 31.89% rarely while only 10.5% never buy it. There is a higher interest in buying SH clothing among women, and among people in the 30-40 age group. This result is somewhat in line with world statistics, according to which 46% of American women aged 18-37 (generations X and Z) usually buy SH fashion (Smith, 2022). As the income is higher, the percentage of those who never buy SH products increases.

The subsequent analyzes included only the respondents who declared themselves consumers of SHC. The results show, that customers consider the seller's location as an important factor when he decides to buy second-hand fashion. Table 2 indicates that most of the consumers prefer brick-and-mortar stores and the majority (55.5%) never buy SHC online. Comparatively, men are the ones who buy online more than women. Online shopping requires some buyer's competencies (knowing how and where to shop online), access to infrastructure (internet, delivery infrastructure), and trust in the sites and offers (consumers are not able to try, feel or touch the products). The survey results yielded no significant difference between female and male respondents regarding open markets SHC buying. Table 3 presents the frequency of purchase of SHC on different platforms by different income groups.

Table 2. Shopping platforms preferred by Romanian SHC buyers

	B&M Stores					Flea Markets					Online Stores				
	Frecvency (N=245)		Percentaj %			Frecvency (N=245)		Percentaj %			Frecvency (N=245)		Percentaj %		
	M	F	M	F	m	M	F	M	F	m	M	F	M	F	m
Always	1	11	1.39	6.36	4.9	2	6	2.78	3.47	3.3	2	1	2.78	0.58	1.2
Often	14	51	19.44	29.48	26.5	9	20	12.50	11.56	11.8	4	4	5.56	2.31	3.3
Sometimes	24	50	33.33	28.90	30.2	28	43	38.89	24.86	29.0	13	31	18.06	17.92	18.0
Rarely	30	56	41.67	32.37	35.1	27	61	37.50	35.26	35.9	20	34	27.78	19.65	22.0
Never	3	5	4.17	2.89	3.3	6	43	8.33	24.86	20.0	33	103	45.83	59.54	55.5
	72	173	100	100	100	72	173	100	100	100	72	173	100	100	100
σ	5.84	53.51				10.29	13.98				22.21	60.11			

Table 3. Frequency of purchase of SHC on different platforms by different income groups

	Frecvency (N=245)			Percentaj (%)			
	under 1500	1501-3500	above 3501	under 1500	1501-3500	above 3501	xi
B&M Stores							
Always	7	2	3	10.45	1.80	4.48	4.9
Often	17	32	16	25.37	28.83	23.88	26.5
Sometimes	23	39	35	34.33	35.14	52.24	39.6
Rarely	17	34	12	25.37	30.63	17.91	25.7
Never	3	4	1	4.48	3.60	1.49	3.3
	67	111	67	100.	100	100	100
Flea Markets							
Always	3	3	2	4.48	2.70	2.99	3.27
Often	7	15	7	10.45	13.51	10.45	11.84
Sometimes	12	34	15	17.91	30.63	22.39	24.90
Rarely	25	41	22	37.31	36.94	32.84	35.92
Never	20	18	21	29.85	16.22	31.34	24.08
	67	111	67	100	100	100	100
Online							
Always	2	1	0	2.99	0.90	0	1.22
Often	1	4	3	1.49	3.60	4.48	3.27
Sometimes	10	28	6	14.93	25.23	8.96	17.96
Rarely	20	17	17	29.85	15.32	25.37	22.04
Never	34	61	41	50.75	54.95	61.19	55.51
	67	111	67	100	100	100	100

The study shows that on average, only 20.17% of the participants buy SH clothes often (monthly) and very often (several times a month). The study shows that, on average, only 20.17% of the participants buy SH clothes often (monthly) and very often (several times a month) and that the majority (66%) declares that the average number of items they purchase in a shopping session is 2-3. The purchase frequency of SH clothing and the average number of items bought in an SHC shopping session is exhibited in table 4.

Table 4. Purchase frequency of SHC and the average number of items bought in a SHC shopping session

	Respondents (238)		Percentaj %	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
SHC Shopping frequency				
Several times a month	2	14	2.78	8.43
Once a month	13	19	18.06	11.45
Rarly (1-2 times a year)	28	52	38.89	31.33
Occasionally	29	81	40.28	48.80
Total	72	166	100.00	100.00
The average number of items bought in a SHC shopping session				
1	9	29	12.50	17.47
2 or 3	44	109	61.11	65.66
4 or 5	13	25	18.06	15.06
more than 5	6	3	8.33	1.81
Total	72	166	100.00	100.00

Regarding the frequency of shopping during the COVID-19 pandemic, 49.8% of the respondents declare that it has decreased and only 7% declare that it has intensified. The minimal mobility, the low social activity, and the uncertainty induced by the pandemic have generated a series of consequences and impacts not only on the retail of new clothes but also on the second-hand ones. Flea markets were closed and the activity of brick and mortar stores decreased. The only platforms that worked were the online ones, they had a huge growth in the new clothing market and were insignificant in the SH one.

By highlighting the role that environmental concern plays in explaining attitudes towards second-hand shopping, the practical implications of this work are possibilities to inspire retailers to add or start second-hand fashion businesses. It is useful to understand the customer of the immediate future who is increasing his purchasing demands and has an interest in second-hand shopping.

The findings have implications for SHC retail managers of both bricks-and-mortar, open markets, and online service outlets in the areas of segmentation, targeting, and retail mix strategies. With this study, information is offered for entrepreneurs, managers, and fashion industry players to rethink, restructure and remodel the post-pandemic market according to the change in consumer behavior and the possibilities of commerce represented by second-hand items.

References

Arora, N., Charm, T., Grimmelt, A., Ortega, M., Robinson, K., Sexauer, C., & Yamakawa, N.
2020

A global view of how consumer behavior is changing amid COVID-19. *Mckinsey and Company*.

Cuc S.

2016

Economia circulară -o soluție pentru industria de textile și pielărie, Ed.Universitatii din Oradea

ECDC

2022

SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern as of 15 July 2022, [Online] available at <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/covid-19/variants-concern>, (accessed 20 July 2022).

Edbring, E.G., Lehner, M. and Mont, O.

2016

Exploring consumer attitudes to alternative models of consumption: motivations and barriers, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, June, Vol. 123,pp.5-15

Evans, F., Grimmer, L., and Grimmer, M.

2022

Consumer orientations of secondhand fashion shoppers: The role of shopping frequency and store type. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 67, 102991.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clcb.2022.100008>

Ferraro, C., Sands, S., and Brace-Govan, J.

2016

The role of fashionability in second-hand shopping motivations. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 32, 262-268.

Kozlov, M.

2022

Monkeypox goes global: why scientists are on alert. *Nature*, 606(7912), 15-16.

Liao, S. and Chu, H.

2013

Influence of consumer online resale awareness on purchase decisions: a mental accounting perspective, *European Journal of Marketing*, vol. 47, no. 10

Lopez, C. and Ouattara, F.

2021

Customer engagement in second-hand fashion marketplaces after the pandemic.

McKinsey

2022

State of Fashion 2022: An uneven recovery and new frontiers, [Online], available at:

<https://www.mckinsey.com/~/media/mckinsey/industries/retail/our%20insights/state%20of%20fashion/2022/the-state-of-fashion-2022.pdf> (accessed 12 June 2022).

MKOR

2022

Market Oportunity Research [Online], available at: https://mkor.ro/fashion-consumer-trends-live/?utm_campaign=fashionroute#ulp-Eosm3mJQML2nCdCm (accessed 20 July 2022).

Pereira, L., Carvalho, R., Dias, Á., Costa, R. and António, N.

2021

How does sustainability affect consumer choices in the fashion industry?. *Resources*, 10(4), 38. <https://doi.org/10.3390/resources10040038>

Risco

2022

[Online] available at <https://www.risco.ro/v3/analiza-sectoriala/caen/C>(accessed 22 June 2022).

Roopa, S. and Rani, M. S.

2012

Questionnaire designing for a survey. *Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society*, 46(4_suppl1), 273-277.

Ruiz-Real, J.L.; Uribe-Toril, J.; Gázquez-Abad, J.C. and de Pablo-Valenciano, J.

2018

Sustainability and Retail: Analysis of Global Research. *Sustainability* 11, 14.

Smith,P

2022

[Online], available <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1008266/share-of-women-who-bought-secondhand-apparel-footwear-or-accessories-by-age-worldwide/>,

ThredUp

2022

2021 resale report, [Online], available at: <https://www.thredup.com/resale/#size-andimpact> (accessed 20 June 2022).

Wiederhold, M. and Martinez, L. F.

2018

Ethical consumer behaviour in Germany: The attitude-behaviour gap in the green apparel industry. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 42(4), 419-429.

Zaman, M., Park, H., Kim, Y. K. and Park, S. H.

2019

Consumer orientations of second-hand clothing shoppers. *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing*, 10(2), 163-176.

Zhao, J.

2022

The Impact of Fashion Industry Due to Covid-19. In *2022 7th International Conference on Social Sciences and Economic Development (ICSSSED 2022)* (pp. 890-894). Atlantis Press.